

Exchange capacity of soils, metal mobilization and soil pollution by heavy metals in West Bengal

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Exchangeable and non-exchangeable (obtainable under stress conditions) capacities of K-ion (and of other ions like Na⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺) and metal mobilization (Na, K, Ca, Mg, Ba, Mn, Fe, Cr, Ni, Cu, Zn) in soils from different regions of West Bengal were examined. The results show that the exchange capacities of selected soil samples are good. The exchangeable and non-exchangeable (obtainable under stress conditions) K-contents are fairly good [1.03–8.5% of the total K (exchangeable) and 4.3–18% of the total K (non-exchangeable)]. Hg is conspicuously absent. There is appreciable metal mobilization and the results are interpreted in terms of concentration factor F_M and the enrichment factor EF. However, in view of very low Al contents (compared to natural abundance), EF values become abnormally high. The results in terms of F_M values suggest depletion of Al (abnormal), Fe (fairly high), K and Mg (fairly high) and enrichment of Ba, Ni and Zn in most cases. There is no appreciable depletion or enrichment for Cu, Cr (except in Patharpratima) and Mn. Na concentrations are high. Bi content is also fairly high indicating the possibility of presence of As and Sb. Metal requirements for plants and microbes must be different from their macroscopic concentrations in soils and in absence of true pollutional limits of metals in soils, comparison of the results are difficult. However, metal mobilization cannot be regarded to be alarming in soils though the concentrations of some metals are on the increase.

Soil and sediments are the ultimate repository or sink of all wastes coming from atmosphere, hydrosphere and biosphere and once waste materials enter the soil, they become part of a cycle that affects all forms of life^{1–3}. Sediments are soils but more intimately involved with water. Sediments are usually river-borne clay, silt, sand, organic and other materials. Metals, though, may not be present in large quantities in soils and sediments but are important and necessary constituents for agricultural, microbial, animal, biogeochemical and engineering requirements^{1–10}.

However, the natural equilibria of elements in soils are heavily disturbed due to increased imports of undesirable substances known as pollutants from different sources. Pollution is an undesirable change in physical, chemical or biological characteristics of water, air and soil from natural sources and mainly from anthropogenic sources that may harmfully affect human, animal and plant life, industrial progress, living conditions and cultural aspects.

Heavy metals are unique class of pollutants (toxicants). The most common heavy metal pollutants are As, Cd, Cr, Cu, Hg, Ni, Pb, Zn, Mn and U. Iron and Al cannot be re-

garded as pollutants but excess is definitely detrimental.

The metals (Zn, Fe, Cu, Mn, Ni, Mo, Co) may prove to be beneficial and act as nutrients for plants and soil microbes but may also be toxic to a lesser or greater degree to humans and animals depending on their concentrations. Therefore, it is desirable to know metal mobilization in soils for agricultural, microbial, pollutional, mineralogical, biogeochemical and engineering points of view. These considerations led to examine the metal mobilization in soils selected at random from different parts of West Bengal. However, due to experimental facilities, studies on Al, Cr, Mn, Fe, Ni, Cu, Zn, Ba and Hg in addition to Na, K, Mg could be made. The samples were collected from engineering point of view (construction of road, bridges, dams, etc.), though the samples were collected from agricultural or adjoining agricultural fields or near the riverside. Therefore, in addition to the study of mobilization, studies on exchangeable and non-exchangeable capacities of soils for ions like K⁺ (particularly) and associated ions (Na⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺) were also undertaken. The results are given in the present communication.

Results and discussion

The abundance of metal ions in soils and crust is given in Table 1^{2,5,6}. There is, of course, a divergence of values regarding the abundance of metals in crusts and soils^{3,5,6}. The concentrations of exchangeable and non-exchangeable ions in soils together with the total metal ion concentrations are presented in Table 2 and Table 3. The values if multiplied by 2.24 give the amount in kg/ha.

Table 1. Natural abundance of metals in soils from literature (mg/kg)

Metal	American soils ⁶	Bowen crust ^{5,6}	Vauloon ²
Na	12000	23000	28300
K	15000	21000	25900
Mg	9000	23000	209000
Ba	580	500	-
Fe	26000	41000	50000
Cu	25	50	50
Cr	54	100	100
Ni	19	80	80
Zn	60	75	75
Mn	550	950	950
Al	72000	82000	81300
Ca			36300

The exchangeable K-concentrations of the soils are appreciable (ranging from 1.03–2.5% of the total K except Raiganj) and in some places are very high (ranging from 4.3–8.5% of the total K for Patharpratima, Sagar and Haldia). This may be due to K-deposit in the salts and clays in this region or K-is not firmly attached to the mineral. The non-exchangeable K-concentrations (K-under stress conditions determined by Pratt's method¹¹) are also fairly good. The values (in terms of % of the total K) are about 18% in Patharpratima and Haldia, around 10% in Haora and Bhatol but about 5% in other places except Raiganj. In general, in all cases K-concentrations of soil studied by us are much less than the usual or average K-concentrations in crustal surfaces or soils. This means depletion of highly soluble K probably due to leaching or utilization of K by plants.

However, total Na-concentrations in the samples are much higher than Na-concentrations in crustal surfaces or soil in all cases, i.e. enrichment of Na in soils. Excess Na-deposition near the sea or sagar islands is expected.

But percent (of the total) exchangeable and non-exchangeable Na-contents are much lower than those of K, though total Na-concentrations are much higher. Total Ca²⁺

Table 2. Exchangeable and non-exchangeable ions in soils and their percentages against total concentrations of metal ions (mg/kg)

Sample and site	Soil order	Potassium				Sodium				Magnesium				Calcium	
		Ex	Non-ex	% of total Ex	% of total non-ex	Ex	Non-ex	% of total Ex	% of total non-ex	Ex	Non-ex	% of total Ex	% of total non-ex	Ex	Non-ex
RS-31 Dhamua N-24 Pargs.	Alfisol	78	339.3	1.26	5.46	289.8	910.8	0.87	2.73	680.4	1507.8	8.27	18.33	3680	7520
RS-93 Bhatol N-Dinajpur (Nagari River)	Entisol	140.4	858	1.71	10.48	140.3	200.1	0.47	0.67	121.5	607.5	2.05	10.27	720	1280
RS-78 Patharpratima S-24 Pargs.	Entisol	819	2074.8	7.00	17.72	448.5	1916	15.91	6.8	216.25	381.5	2.86	5.05	1004	132
RS-27 Raiganj (N-Dinajpur)	Alfisol	78	62.4	1.03	0.83	200.1	50.6	0.78	0.19	88.7	93.55	1.81	1.91	504	196
RS-1 Haora	Entisol	538.2	1197.3	4.30	9.57	529.0	310.5	1.56	0.92	437.4	899.1	6.13	12.60	1200	1200
RS-71 Medinipur (Slit of Subarna rekha)	Entisol	101.4	276.9	1.88	5.12	158.7	101.2	0.42	0.27	194.4	534.6	10.8	29.7	880	120
RS-II Sagar	Entisol	249.6	487.5	2.51	4.91	5000.2	1398.4	14.88	4.16	992.65	708.34	15.44	11.02	1064	936
RS-36 Haldia	Entisol	768.3	1673.1	8.48	18.47	1998.7	450.8	6.15	1.39	572.26	2344.95	6.29	25.80	6784	16

Ex = exchangeable, Non-ex = Non-exchangeable

ion in soils was not determined but total Mg^{2+} contents were determined. It is apparent that total Mg^{2+} content (exchangeable and non-exchangeable as determined in the present work) are considerable compared to the total amount of Mg^{2+} content. However, Mg^{2+} concentrations in the soil samples appear to be low in all cases compared to the total Mg^{2+} content in earth's crust. It can be assumed that Na^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions are more easily leached than K^+ ion from the minerals, may be due to its effective size and consequent attachment with the mineral, a natural safeguard against exhaustive leaching of K^+ ion due to its solubility.

The concentrations of Ba are always much higher but nil in some places. The reasons for the presence or absence of Ba are not known. Ba may occur along with Ca and Mg from the radioactive disintegration of heavier atoms. Ba salts are also used in fireworks and low explosives. Ba may be mobilized in soils from the debris of fireworks and low explosives.

Bowen⁵, de Haan and Zwerman¹², Purves¹³, Sawine¹⁴ have reviewed the different aspects of metal mobilization and soil pollution. The soil is important habitat for both

producers (green plants) and decomposers (bacteria and fungi). Most soils have considerable buffering capacity with respect to contaminants and they are themselves very slow (kiloyears) self-purifying. Thus biological effects of contaminations appear slowly and take many years for correction. Naturally soil contamination should be minimized as far as practicable.

Population explosion leads to increased food production with increased application of manures, fertilizers and insecticides causing environmental pollution and ecological imbalances. Air, water and soils are being polluted to an alarming extent endangering plant, animal and human kingdom.

Toxic elements if they reach the soil, become a part of the life cycle of

But due to microbial interactions, biomagnifications and bioamplifications, these elements may accumulate in animal and human body tissues to toxic levels.

The pollutants leached into underground water may be

Table 3. Metal mobilization of soils in West Bengal (mg/kg) and their concentration (F_M) and enrichment factor (EF)

Sample	Parameter	Al	Na	K	Mg	Ba	Fe	Cu	Cr	Ni	Zn	Mn
	Conc.	940	33300	6215	8222	1128	19410	45	32.5	62.5	322	544
RS-31	F_M	0.01	1.44	0.29	0.357	2.25	0.47	0.9	0.32	0.78	4.29	0.57
	EF		126.3	25.81	31.18	196.8	41.29	78.51	28.35	68.15	374.52	49.95
	Conc.	2780	30012	8187	5915	1154	24630	30	35	67.5	169	844
RS-93	F_M	0.04	1.3	0.39	0.257	2.3	0.60	0.6	0.35	0.84	2.25	0.88
	EF		38.48	11.5	7.58	68.07	17.71	17.69	10.32	24.88	66.46	16.89
	Conc.	2880	28187	11710	7555	800	21300	57.5	265	170	150	271
RS-78	F_M	0.04	1.22	0.55	0.328	1.6	0.52	1.15	2.65	2.12	2.0	0.28
	EF		34.89	15.87	9.35	45.55	14.79	32.74	75.45	60.50	56.94	8.12
	Conc.	4840	25737	7550	4895	Nil	21630	25	105	137.5	122	330
RS-27	F_M	0.07	1.12	0.36	0.212		0.52	0.5	1.05	1.71	1.62	0.34
	EF		18.95	6.09	3.60		8.93	8.47	17.79	29.12	27.56	5.88
	Conc.	810	33912	12512	7135	Nil	13800	27.5	20	92.5	1345	483
RS-1	F_M	0.01	1.47	0.59	0.31		0.33	0.55	0.20	1.15	17.93	0.50
	EF		149.26	60.31	31.40		34.07	55.67	20.24	117.05	1815.45	51.46
	Conc.	780	37375	5400	1800	1155	14880	42.5	47.5	77.5	141	720
RS-71	F_M	0.01	1.62	0.25	0.078	2.31	0.36	0.85	0.47	0.96	1.88	0.75
	EF		170.83	27.03	8.23	242.84	38.15	89.35	49.93	101.84	197.64	79.67
	Conc.	2220	33612	9925	6427	3205	16600	47.5	255	217.5	541	858
RS-11	F_M	0.03	1.46	0.47	0.28	6.41	0.40	0.95	2.55	2.71	7.21	0.90
	EF		53.97	17.45	10.32	236.76	14.95	35.09	94.19	100.42	266.43	33.36
	Conc.	1750	32475	9060	9087	4205	15810	45	257.5	147.5	262	777
RS-36	F_M	0.02	1.41	0.43	0.395	8.41	0.38	0.9	2.57	1.84	3.49	0.81
	EF		66.16	20.21	18.51	394.06	18.06	42.17	120.65	86.39	163.68	38.32

utilized by plant uptake. However, there is always a background concentration of common metals and other elements on earth's surface and their observed levels are different in different places as evident from the metal concentrations of soils from different places given in Table 3.

Hg concentrations could not be determined in the samples. It is apparent that pollutant load is different in different places and the values are widely variable. However, in view of lack of data, it is difficult to compare our values with values given by other workers.

Sposito has given a list of EF (enrichment factor) values defined as ($M_{\text{soil}}/M_{\text{crust}}$) based on the elemental content (in mg/kg) of soil (USA) and crustal rocks (Bowen)⁵. According to Sposito⁶, values of EF in the range 0.5–2.0 about the value 1.0 represent no relative depletion or enrichment, EF values <0.5 indicate significant depletion, EF between 2–10 means enrichment and EF >10 indicates strong enrichment.

Our evaluation is similar but differ slightly. The enrichment or depletion of the elements^{15–18} in soils can be roughly estimated from the concentration factor (F_M) instead of EF of Sposito⁶ defined as

$$F_M = [M]_{\text{soil}}/[M]_{\text{natural}}$$

Bowen's data were utilized for $[M]_{\text{natural}}$ or $[M]_{\text{crust}}$.

However, the enrichment of metals can be better represented by the enrichment factor defined as

$$EF = \frac{[x]_{\text{soil}}/[Al]_{\text{soil(exp.)}}}{[x]_{\text{fr}}/[Al]_{\text{fr}}}$$

where $[x]_{\text{soil}}$ is the average concentration of elements $[x]$ in the sediment, $[x]_{\text{fr}}$ is the average concentration of $[x]$ in the superficial fresh rock, $[Al]_{\text{fr}}$ and $[Al]_{\text{soil}}$ are the average Al content in superficial fresh rock and in the soil. Al is moderately toxic to the plants, but relatively less available due to high pH of soils.

Al is chosen as standard as it is poorly soluble and is considered not to be affected by pollution. Al present in aluminosilicate minerals (e.g. Feldspar etc.) is essential on a time scale of years or decades. It is assumed that Al has reached steady state at the continental surface i.e. not at present being accumulated by the soil layer and is derived only from land erosion, a natural process. Natural process of erosion would occur and this is not termed pollution. The enrichment factor can be estimated assuming

$$\frac{[x]_{\text{fr}}}{[Al]_{\text{fr}}} \approx \frac{[x]_{\text{natural}}}{[Al]_{\text{natural}}}$$

Both increase or decrease in EF means accumulation and depletion of the metal from soils due to a large number of factors and can be regarded as pollution.

EF values indicate relative enrichment and depletion of the element from the environment and are of importance from biogeochemical point of view.

The metal concentrations, F_M and EF values of the elements in soils are given in Table 3. The results suggest enormous depletion for Al, Fe, and considerable depletion for K and Mg but enrichment in Ba, Ni and Zn is noticed in most cases. There is no appreciable enrichment or depletion for Cu, Cr (except in Patharpratima) and Mn. Considerable enrichment of Na is observed in all cases. Bi concentrations are fairly high. Bi belongs to the same group as As. It is possible that As and Sb are also present in considerable amounts but estimation of As and Sb is not possible.

Variation of metal mobilization from place to place is natural. Enrichment or depletion of metals are due to physical and chemical weathering processes, formation of soluble or insoluble complexes and leaching, inputs from industrial processes, effluent discharges, nutrient recycling (like organic manures), agricultural, fertilizers, insecticides, pesticides etc. The deposition or removal of sediments, fly ashes etc. carried by the rivers from the upper reaches and deposition or removal of sediments by tidal waves (like Haldia, Patharpratima, Sagar etc.) are other important contributing factors.

Metals like K, Fe, Mn, Zn, Cu are essential for plants in small amounts but toxic at higher doses. The elements like Fe, Ni, Cu, Mn, Zn etc. are essential for human health and microbial population in small doses.

But the macroscopic concentrations of metal ions in soil (as determined) obviously will be much higher than the microscopic concentrations required by plants and microbes. But the bioavailability of metal ions will be different and much less due to different complex interactions, complexations redox-reactions etc. occurring in soils.

Though the pollutional aspects of water have been studied in details and the upper pollutional limits of metal ions are known but similar data for soil pollution are not known with certainty. Therefore, concentration factors F_M can be taken as criteria of pollution.

The results show that the metal mobilization or depletion in soils cannot be regarded to be alarming but definitely appreciable in some cases.

Experimental

The soil samples were collected at different depths (6"–

50") by directly boring using suitable methods like auger, rotary boring, driving sampler or drilling. The samples were homogeneously mixed to make representative samples. The soil samples in different locations were taken in containers, sealed with wax to prevent moisture loss and sent to laboratory for testing.

The samples were examined for moisture contents in the usual way. The dried samples were powdered and used as specified. The extractions of the metal ions (Na, K, Mg, Ba, Mn, Fe, Ni, Cr, Cu, Zn, Al, Bi) (and the extraction of aluminium separately) were carried out in the way suggested by Black, Jackson and others^{19,20}. Al in the soil was estimated spectrophotometrically at 520 nm using aluminon reagent in buffer solution (pH 4.2) and Fe was estimated spectrophotometrically at 510 nm as ferroin using a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer (Model Lambda 20). Cu, Cr, Ni were estimated using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer Model A analyst 300 (Perkin-Elmer). For the estimation of total K, Na, Ba, Mg, Mn, Zn, Hg, Bi, the instrument used was Analytical Jena, AAS Vario (with auto dilution and AS 52 auto sampler attachments). Measurements were taken in 5 mean cycles with regression coefficient ranging from 0.981 to 1.00 for different metals. Presence of Hg proved negative for all samples.

The exchange capacity of soils were determined by treating 10 g of soil sample with 250 ml of 1M of ammonium acetate (pH = 7) solution in an Erlenmeyer flask in a shaker. The mixture was filtered and stored in polyethylene bottles. Non-exchangeable K from soils was determined following the method of Pratt¹¹ by resorting to one time extraction by boiling with 1 N HNO₃. In this method, soil : acid (1 : 10) suspension was allowed to boil gently for 15 min over sandbath. K-extracted in this way minus K-extracted by neutral 1N NH₄OAc gave the non-exchangeable K-of the soil. Step-K values²¹ are indices for non-exchangeable K-values of the soil. But step-K values were not determined, as the plants are not expected to utilize K under such drastic conditions and in view of pollution aspects (repeated treatment of soil with HNO₃ and their disposal) the determination of step-K should be limited unless very essential.

Exchangeable Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ were estimated using EDTA in the usual way^{19,20}. Exchangeable and non-exchangeable Na⁺ and K⁺ were determined using a Systronics Digital Flame Photometer (Model 125).

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